

ADVANCES IN HIGH PERFORMANCE THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

I. Y. CHANG, A. K. DHINGRA AND J. K. LEES
(E. I. Du Pont de Nemours and Company, Inc., Composites Center,
Wilmington, Delaware 19880-0702, USA)

ABSTRACT

A review is made of principal thermoplastic matrix composites and processing methods used to fabricate them. Included is a comparison of the neat matrix resins' properties and the matrix-dominated mechanical properties of thermoplastic composites. Innovative process developments in thermoplastic composites are also reviewed and discussed.

MATERIAL SYSTEMS DEVELOPMENT

1. Thermoplastic Matrix Resins

Several high-performance thermoplastic resins are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. High-performance thermoplastic matrix systems.

Polymer	Company	Chemical Description
J-Polymer	Du Pont	A polyamide copolymer based on bis (para-amino cyclohexyl) methane
PEKK	Du Pont	Poly(ether-ketone-ketone)
K-Polymer	Du Pont	A polyimide derived from an aromatic diethyl ester diacid with an aromatic diamine
N-Polymer	Du Pont	Polyimide from 6FTA with p- and m-phenylene diamine
PEEK	ICI	Poly(ether-ether-ketone)
HTX	ICI	A polyarylene ether ketone derivative
PPS	Phillips	Poly(phenylene-sulfide)
PAS-2	Phillips	A polyarylene sulfide derivative
"Ultem" PEI	GE	Polyetherimide
"Radel" PES	Amoco	A polyarylene ether sulfone derivative
"Torlon" PAI	Amoco	Polyamideimide

These thermoplastic polymers have relatively high T_g as compared with other engineering resins such as PET and nylon 66. Due to high T_g and high melt viscosity of these resins, a relatively high processing temperature (T_p) is required for fabrication and consolidation of the composites. In particular, K-polymer (Du Pont)¹, HTX (ICI)², PAS-2 (Phillips)³ and "Radel" PES (Amoco) with T_g above 200°C were recently developed as high-performance matrix candidates for carbon fiber reinforced composites. These thermoplastic resins have high toughness superior to aerospace epoxies such as Narmco's 5208 or Hercules 3501. The semi-crystalline thermoplastic polymers (PEEK, PEKK, HTX) are generally more resistant to organic solvents than the amorphous polymers such as PEI, PES and PAS-2. It has been found, however, that the amorphous K-polymer and N-polymer⁴ have excellent solvent resistance. "Torlon" as a polyamideimide (PAI) has excellent mechanical properties but is sensitive to moisture due to presence of amide groups in the polymer chains. A new semi-crystalline polyetherketoneketone (PEKK) polymer is being developed at Du Pont as a potential high performance thermoplastic matrix system for advanced composites⁵. This resin with upper use temperature between those of K-polymer (polyimide) and J-polymer (polyamide) has potential advantages such as retention of mechanical properties in hot-wet environment or after exposure in organic solvents and excellent flame resistance. K-polymer and N-polymer with dry T_g at 250°C and 350°C, respectively, show excellent properties and are suitable for high use-temperature applications^{1,4}. The thermoplastic neat resin properties are given in Tables 2 and 3. Comparison of matrix systems is given in Table 4.

Table 2. Thermal, morphological and rheological properties of neat resins.

Polymer	T _g (°C) ^a	T _m (°C) ^b	T _p (°C) ^c	Crystallinity ^d (%)	Viscosity ^e (Pa.S)
J-Polymer	156	None	300	None	1000
PEKK	156	338	370	26	2500
K-Polymer	250	None	350	None	>10,000
N-Polymer	350	None	375	None	> 100,000
PEEK	144	340	380	33	3500
HTX	205	386	420	20	-----
PPS	85	285	343	-----	-----
PAS-2	215	None	330	None	-----
PEI	217	None	343	None	2000
PES	260	None	330	None	-----
PAI	288	None	350	None	>10,000

^a Glass transition temperature (dry). ^b Melt temperature. ^c Nominal processing temperature. ^d X-ray diffraction. ^e At processing temperature, 10 sec⁻¹ shear rate.

Table 3. Mechanical and fracture toughness properties of neat resins

Polymer	Density	Modulus ^a	Strength ^b	Elongation ^c	Fracture Energy ^d
	g/cm ³	GPa	MPa	%	KJ/m ²
Epoxy	-----	4.28	83	1	0.1
J-polymer	1.16	3.17	103	25	2.0
PEKK	1.30	4.50	102	4	1.0
K-Polymer	1.31	3.76	102	14	1.8
N-Polymer	1.44	4.17	110	6	2.5
PEEK	1.30	3.79	103	11	2.0
HTX	-----	2.48	86	13	-----
PPS	1.36	3.91	80	3	-----
PAS-2	1.40	3.28	101	8	-----
PEI	1.27	2.96	104	60	2.5
PES	-----	2.41	76	7	-----
PAI	1.38	3.30	136	25	3.4

^a Tensile or flexural modulus. ^b Tensile strength. ^c Tensile elongation. ^d G_{1C} from compact tension test ASTM-E399.

Table 4. Performance comparison of matrix systems

Polymer	Mechanical	Toughness	Environmental Stability		
			Heat	Moisture	Solvent
Epoxy	++	-	++	-	++
J-polymer	++	++	+	+	+
PEKK	++	++	++	++	++
K-Polymer	++	++	++	++	++
N-Polymer	++	++	++	++	++
PEEK	++	++	++	++	++
HTX	++	++	++	++	++
PPS	+	++	+	++	++
PAS-2	++	++	++	++	+
PEI	++	++	++	++	+
PES	+	++	++	++	+
PAI	++	++	++	+	++

++ Excellent. + Fair - Poor

2. Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic Composites

Mechanical properties of the thermoplastic laminates are listed in Table 5.

Table 5. Mechanical properties of thermoplastic composites reinforced with carbon fiber ^a

Matrix	Flexural Strength	Short Beam Shear	Compression Strength	G _{1c} KJ/m ²	Compression After Impact ^b	
	MPa	MPa	MPa		Stress MPa	Strain %
J-polymer	1450	104	1040	1.1	345	0.75
PEKK	1620	117	1390	1.0	274	0.60
K-Polymer	1590	98	1000	1.7	274	0.65
N-Polymer	1530	120	-----	-----	-----	-----
PEEK	1500	117	1040	1.6	310	0.70
HTX	1770	-----	1130	2.2	301	0.63
PPS	1360 (1610)	69	635 (908)	0.9	179	0.52
PAS-2	1650 (1920)	-----	897 (977)	-----	-----	-----
PEI	-----	94	824	1.2	-----	-----
PES	-----	78	-----	-----	248	-----
PAI	2070	110	1380	1.6	345	0.90

^a Unidirectional laminates with nominal 60% fiber volume.

^b With quasi-isotropic specimen and 67 J/cm impact energy.

The most important feature of these composites is their high Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{1c}) by the double cantilever beam test and superior damage tolerance performance as measured by the compression-after-impact test.

PROCESS DEVELOPMENTS

In contrast to thermosetting processes which must deal with the chemical reaction that leads to crosslinking, thermoplastic processes must focus on polymer rheology. This increases the importance of the prepreg form in the total process stream and requires alternate process concepts than those used for thermosets.

1. Impregnation Processes

The choice of a prepreg system is very important as it relates to subsequent process steps. As a result, four different methods of prepregging are currently being used.

A. Solvent Impregnation: This process has several drawbacks: the potential for residual solvent in the prepreg, and inability to use higher performance resins that have excellent solvent resistance. In addition to environmental restrictions, investment would be required to recover the solvent.

B. Melt Impregnation: Three basic approaches are used to achieve this type of preform: (a) film stacking with either a roll or belt type continuous process to melt the resin and work it into the yarn bundle; (b) adding the matrix as a powder then melt it and work it into the yarn bundle; (c) direct melt injection into the yarn bundle. In the first two cases it is necessary to prepare the matrix resin for use in these processes. The third approach makes a partially consolidated tow that is flexible enough to be woven into a fabric.

C. Comingling Process: It requires a texturing process to open the yarn bundle without damaging the brittle fiber. This is particularly difficult to accomplish for a high filament count carbon tow such as 6K or 12K AS-4. The comingled product cannot be used effectively in high speed process like filament winding because of the lack of bundle integrity.

D. Powder Impregnation: This process generally produces a flexible tape or tow. There are two published methods. The Atochem process encapsulates the thermoplastic resin powder in the yarn with a sheath of either the same resin or a lower melting point resin. The disadvantage of this method is that the composite laminate produced from the encapsulated tows may contain excessive resin-rich areas. A second approach is that employed by BASF⁶ wherein the powder is put in an aqueous suspension that is then used to impregnate the fibers. The most important advantage of powder impregnation is its ability to process matrix systems with very high melt viscosity and high melt temperature. However, there are two major concerns for the powder impregnated preregs. The unidirectional carbon prepreg has weak transverse strength and requires a relatively large amount of polymeric binding agent such as 6% of a polyacrylic acid by weight of matrix resin⁷ which may stay in the system.

2. Thermoformable Sheet

An innovative method for handling the manufacture of formed complex shapes is to use a thermoformable sheet with oriented discontinuous fiber structure as developed at Du Pont⁸. The sheet is designed such that the filament reinforcement (3-15 cm length) is aligned in each layer to such a degree that continuous fiber-like properties result. The discontinuous fiber reinforcement, however, does permit the drawing with complex shapes.

3. Filament Winding

For the most effective and low cost process it is desirable to directly consolidate the prepreg during the winding step such as in-situ consolidation being developed at Du Pont⁹. In this particular case the time for heat up and consolidation is in the order of seconds. It appears that the fiber winding at economically attractive rates is possible.

4. 3D Braiding

The primary focus has been on the formation of the structure with high fracture toughness. A new process with "in-line" consolidation was developed at Du Pont for forming 3D braids with thermoplastic melt impregnated tows that can form a wide range of structure shapes¹⁰.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

To demonstrate manufacture of thermoplastic composite parts with cost reduction will be a major challenge for the aerospace industry and the material suppliers. Effort will focus on design, manufacture and testing of large complex-shape thermoplastic composite parts. As a leading manufacturer of advanced material systems, Du Pont will continue to develop the innovative processing technology and the material systems with optimum performance.

REFERENCES

1. Boyce RJ, Gannett TP, Gibbs HH and Wedgewood AR, 32nd International SAMPE Symposium, Anaheim, California, (1987), 169.
2. Cogswell FD, Leach DC, Mc Grail PT, Colquhoun HM, MacKenzie P, Turner RM, Ibid, 382.
3. Linstrom MR and Campbell RW, Ibid, 147.
4. Gupta D, SME Conference on Tooling for Composites, Los Angeles, California (1988).
5. Chang IY, The SAMPE Quarterly, 19 (4) (1988) 29.
6. Hartness T, 33rd International SAMPE Symposium, (1988), 7.
7. International Patent Application PCT/US87/02867 (1987).
8. Okine RK, Edison DH. and Little NK, 32rd International SAMPE Symposium, (1987), 1413.
9. Egerton MW and Gruber MB, 33rd International SAMPE Symposium, (1988) 35.
10. Popper P and Mc Connell R, 32nd International SAMPE Symposium, (1987), 92.